

Keloid in Nigeria: More questions than answers

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majority of these beliefs are wrong. The erroneous beliefs about Keloids among Nigerians, most importantly the cosmetic deformity associated with it, have contributed negatively to the well-being of keloid formers, hence making the condition a source of psychological trauma for them.

Here, we highlight the current situation of keloids within the Nigerian populace to raise pertinent questions with answers. This will help to ultimately chart a new course for the awareness, acquire a better understanding of the pathogenesis, genetics, and socio-cultural factors associated with Keloids among Nigerians.

Keywords: Keloid, Pathogenesis, Cosmetic, Trauma, Genetics

INTRODUCTION

The term Keloid, derived from the Greek word ‘chele’, meaning crab’s claw, was first used in 1806 by Alibert to describe cutaneous fibrosis because of its distinguishing processes (Louw, 2000). Keloids are excessive scar tissues that grow beyond the margin of the original wound. They are a form of pseudo-malignant growth which develops sequel to the wound healing process in genetically predisposed individuals (Bienias, Miękoś-Zydek, & Kaszuba, 2011). Keloid scars, otherwise known as cutaneous fibrosis, are distinguishable from other raised scars by having claw-like erythematous processes (Janssen de Limpens & Cormane, 1982). Keloid presents as smooth, globular, shiny swellings having the same color as that of the surrounding skin of the wounds that

ABSTRACT

Nigeria reported an estimated incidence of 1.5 million in the year 2017 making it one of the highest reasons for dermatology and plastic surgery consults in Nigeria to date. The current available prevalence does not represent the true prevalence of the condition as majority of the keloid affected individuals (Keloid formers) either resort to unorthodox/traditional therapies while majority do not seek therapy at all. Several hypotheses have been propounded for the pathogenesis of Keloids with no clear definition of the development of the condition. As with its pathogenesis, a definite inheritance pattern has not been established for Keloids. Results from genome wide association studies in different populations have yielded different results of possible candidate loci.

Although very common in Nigeria, its awareness within the population is still very low, with several prevailing beliefs about the causes of Keloids within the population. However,

precipitate it. Keloids develop within three months to a year after the wound healing (Robles & Berg, 2007). Although not fatal, Keloids present with a range of morbidities such as pain, erythema, itchiness, cosmetic unsightliness, and functional impairments (Devika & Arockiamary, 2011). Keloids constitute a source of emotional and psychological trauma to affected individuals, clinically referred to as keloid formers (Olasode, 2010). Based on the mode of occurrence, Keloids can be classified as primary or spontaneous when they occur idiopathically or secondary when they occur as a consequence of a trauma to the skin. Primary Keloids are thought to account for as much as a third of all cases (Olabanji & Oladele, 2011). Keloids affect all age groups; however, they reach peak incidence between the

second and fourth decade of life (Salami & E Irekpita, 2011).

PREVALENCE OF KELOIDS

Keloids are predominantly found among dark-skinned individuals, and this prevalence seems to follow the skin color gradient with Blacks having the highest observed prevalence followed by Hispanics, Asians and the least prevalence among Caucasians (Trace, Enos, Mantel, & Harvey, 2016). An estimated 427,000 physician visits in the United States per year can be attributed to Keloids, with African Americans making up the bulk of this population (Hahn, McFarland, C, & M., 2016). A prevalence of 0.09% was reported among Caucasians of European origin (Brown & Bayat, 2009), with about 6%, 3.5%, and 16% of individuals of West African origin (Henshaw *et al.*, 2015), East African population (Kiprono *et al.*, 2015), and Central African population respectively being keloid formers (Kouotou *et al.*, 2019). Over 1.5 million Nigerians are thought to be Keloid formers in the year 2017, with about 36% of this figure accounted for by familial cases (Olaitan, 2009). Keloids are significantly more frequent in the southern part of the country as compared to the north, although the reason for this disparity remains to be proven (Henshaw *et al.*, 2018).

RISK FACTORS

Several attempts have been made to define the factors that predispose an individual to the development of Keloids. These efforts have identified factors such as Melanin, Genetics, Age, Body Mass Index, Insulin-like Growth factor, among others (Wolfram, Tzankov, Püzl, & Piza-Katzer, 2009). These factors have been demonstrated to be associated with the condition at the epidemiological level; however, further studies aimed at utilizing these factors to describe the pathogenesis of Keloid have been largely inconclusive.

Melanin. The hormone responsible for the pigmentation of the skin has been associated with Keloids (Dyal, 1989). Prevalence figures showed that darker individuals are more predisposed to the development of the disease (Brown & Bayat, 2009). This association appears to be dose dependent, with prevalence higher in dark-skinned individuals than light skinned population, implying an inversely proportional relationship between keloid prevalence

and the quantity or presence of melanin pigment (Andrews, Marttala, Macarak, Rosenbloom, & Uitto, 2016). This hypothesis is supported by the world prevalence figures, with Africans having the highest prevalence, followed by Hispanics, Asians, and Caucasians. Studies have revealed the increased tendency of Keloids to develop in areas of the body where there is a higher concentration of melanocytes (Wolfram *et al.*, 2009). The postulation of melanin as a risk factor is being questioned with the reports of Keloids among albinos (Kiprono *et al.*, 2015).

Genetics. Keloids have long been associated with genetics, with the disease having been established to segregate within families (Santos-Cortez *et al.*, 2017). Individuals with a positive family history of Keloids are at four times higher risk of developing Keloids and eight times more likely to develop keloids at multiple sites, suggesting a strong genetic underpinning factor in the occurrence of Keloids (Belie, Ugburo, & Mofikoya, 2019). Although recently reported to be a polygenic and heterogeneous disease condition (Glass, 2017), studies around the world have established mendelian inheritance patterns for Keloids (Devika & Arockiamary, 2011). It was established to be inherited through the autosomal recessive pattern in the Nigerian population (Omo Dare, 1975). However, this inheritance pattern has not been successfully replicated in Nigeria nor in any other population where keloids are prevalent. Bloom (1956), who studied five Italian family pedigrees, concluded that keloids are inherited in an autosomal dominant fashion, although the expression varies among individuals. This assertion was corroborated by the report of Marneros *et al.* (2001), who in their study of fourteen families from diverse ancestral backgrounds, including African-Americans. Genome-wide association studies have recently established Keloids to be associated with multiple loci; however, there have been varying degrees of replicability in the results from different populations, thus suggesting the involvement of underlying factors (Lu *et al.*, 2018). A GWAS study among the Japanese population showed that SNPs rs873549, rs1511412, and rs8032158 were associated with keloid development (Nakashima *et al.*, 2010). Three SNPs (rs1511412, rs940187, and rs2271289) and rs35641839 were associated with keloids among the Chinese Han population and African-Americans, respectively (Lu *et al.*, 2018; Velez *et al.*, 2014). The

almost non-presence of overlaps of the associated SNPs is suggestive of the heterogeneity of keloids. The genes, haplotypes, and SNPs associated with Keloids among native Africans and Nigerians specifically remain unknown.

Age. Over the years, the incidence of Keloids has been reported to be at its highest within the second and fourth decades of life (Chike-Obi, Cole, & Brissett, 2009). Although no pathological mechanism has been used to explain this association, it could be hypothesized that the effect of sex hormones, which are usually at their highest concentration during this period compared to older people, could be responsible for this association (Shaheen, Khaddam, & Kesh, 2016). Furthermore, young people are also physically more active and are likely to have a greater tendency to sustain trauma compared to older individuals. Keloids are thought to be very rare among children before puberty; however, there is anecdotal evidence of a higher prevalence of keloids within this age group than previously reported (Ayanlowo *et al.*, 2018).

Blood Pressure. Systemic parameters such as blood pressure, body mass index, serum Insulin-like growth factor, and blood group have all been associated with the development of keloids. High Blood Pressure has been reported to be significantly and positively associated with both keloid size and number (Adotama, Rutherford, & Glass, 2015). This association was found to be more prominent in patients below thirty years of age (Rutherford & Glass, 2017). Although unproven, it was suggested that endothelial dysfunction due to high blood pressure could contribute to the development of fibrotic diseases, an example of which is Keloids. Keloids have also been hypothesized to be caused by a hypoxia-induced pathway. Hypertension, on the other hand, has been implicated in inflammation-induced hypoxia, thus substantiating the hypothesis (Ogawa & Akaishi, 2016).

Obesity. High Body Mass Index (BMI), a potent causative factor for hypertension, is thought to be linked with Keloids because of the high circulating levels of leptin, which is common in both obesity and keloid scars (Rutherford & Glass, 2017). Another plausible explanation for the association between obesity and Keloids is the elevated levels of Insulin-like Growth Factor 1 in both conditions (Arima,

Huang, Rosner, Akaishi, & Ogawa, 2015). There are questions about which condition is secondary to the other owing to the obvious psychological trauma Keloids cause for formers, particularly women and young people.

Blood Group. Another systemic parameter implicated in keloid development is the blood group. The association between the interaction of cell surface antigens of red cells of blood group A and certain epithelial cells has been hypothesized to be associated with the development of Keloids among Syrians (Shaheen *et al.*, 2016); however, the association could not be replicated in the West African population (Mouhari-Toure *et al.*, 2012).

HYPOTHESES OF PATHOLOGIC PROCESS IN KELOID

Several attempts have been made to explain the complex synergy between the risk factors and the development of Keloids with little success. A defect in the regulatory negative feedback of collagen synthesis resulting in decreased collagen degradation/production ratio (Olabanji & Oladele, 2011), defect in the apoptotic regulatory mechanism, hypoxia and over production of pro-inflammatory cytokines (Reichenberger, 2012), in addition to telomere shortening (De Felice, Wilson, & Nacca, 2009) are among the leading hypotheses thought to be involved in the pathogenesis of Keloids. The heterogeneity of the genetics and pathogenesis associated with Keloids in different populations raises the question of what answers will be reported among the Native African population and Nigerians, especially. Africa, with its high genetic diversity and high keloid prevalence, offers a veritable avenue for exhaustively explaining the pathogenesis of Keloids. Emerging evidence reveals that keloid scars are not benign tumors, but rather a consequence of chronic inflammatory processes, although evidence of the involvement of the Apoptotic regulatory system in the development of Keloids have been reported (Wu *et al.*, 2012). This strengthens the argument that the pathogenesis of Keloids is still far from being completely understood.

Transforming growth factor beta (TGF- β): Transforming growth factor beta (TGF- β) plays a central role in wound healing and fibrosis, suggesting

its importance in the pathogenesis of Keloids (Bayat *et al.*, 2004). Keloid fibroblasts have been demonstrated to be produced in excess and be overly sensitive to growth factors, especially TGF- β (Penn *et al.*, 2012; Barrientos *et al.*, 2008). Heat Shock Protein (HSP-90), which is induced by both internal and external stress, and consequently leads to increased cell proliferation have been reported to increase the activity of TGF- β in keloidal tissue (Liberski, Marczak, & Migdalski, 2018). Studies have reported an increase in the activity of HSP-90 in keloid tissue (Maderal & Berman, 2016). This is suggestive of a positive feedback loop, which thus perpetuates the growth of keloid tissue. The different positive feedback loops involved in the pathogenesis of keloids might explain the difficulty in achieving a therapeutic index, as none of the available therapeutic approaches targets all the pathogenic pathways of keloids.

Apoptosis. Lower rates of apoptosis have also been reported in keloid scars compared to normal skin. This could be associated with mutations in the apoptosis-regulating genes, including p53 (Wu *et al.*, 2012). This mutation could result in an imbalance between the production and degradation of extracellular matrix (Heitzer *et al.*, 2012).

Keratinocytes. Keratinocytes have been implicated in keloid formation through the in-vitro co-culturing of keratinocytes and fibroblasts, which revealed a higher production of keloid-derived fibroblasts (Lim, Phan, Lim, & Cao, 2009). This increase in turnover could be explained by the increased production of growth factors, hypoxia-inducible factors, and the reduction of apoptosis. This has demonstrated the synergistic effect of keratinocytes and fibroblasts in the development of keloids (Andrews *et al.*, 2016).

CURRENTLY AVAILABLE TREATMENT/MANAGEMENT PROTOCOL FOR KELOIDS FOR NIGERIANS

Keloid treatment remains an enigma to physicians, as no single treatment has been able to permanently cure the condition. This is largely due to the lack of total understanding of the pathogenesis of the condition (Lee & Jang, 2018). Several treatment modalities are currently available in keloid management with varying success rates reported (Shridharani *et al.*, 2010). Characteristics of

the keloid lesion, including location, age, size, etc., are considered in the mode of treatment to be employed for each lesion. However, with all the available treatment options and the differential suitability of such treatments, the results are most often not satisfactory, hence the adoption of a combination of two or more treatment modalities for a single keloid (Olabanji, 2011). The adoption of multiple therapies for the treatment of keloid, though, has significantly increased the success achieved in keloid therapy (Stahl *et al.*, 2010). The associated adverse effects and records of treatment failure continue to necessitate the need for more precise, effective, and safe treatment modalities for keloids. Therapeutic approaches involved in keloid treatment includes but not limited to, pressure therapy, surgery, steroids, immunotherapy, radiotherapy, and chemotherapy (Chike-Obi *et al.*, 2009).

Occlusive dressing: This is a long-established and widely used treatment modality for raised scars in the clinical setting. It involves silicone-based treatment and non-silicone-based treatments (Butler, Longaker, & Yang, 2008). Silicone-based treatment involves the use of topical silicone gel preparation and silicone sheeting (Gauglitz, Korting, Pavicic, Ruzicka, & Jeschke, 2011). The mechanism of this therapy is not clear. However, it is thought that the stratum corneum of the lesion was occluded and hydrated, which subsequently alters the secretion of growth factors that influence fibroblast regulation (Slemp & Kirschner, 2006). Silicone preparations are recommended to be worn for a minimum of 12 hours daily over a period of two months (Mrowietz & Seifert, 2009). About 79% to 90% improvement in keloid scars has been recorded in the use of these occlusive dressing but never has 100% therapy been achieved (Chike-Obi *et al.*, 2009). The success of this therapy is usually limited due to non-compliance by patients. Skin maceration and excoriation are among the identified adverse effects of silicone preparations (Davidson, Aziz, Rashid, & Khachemoune, 2009).

Compression therapy. This is largely used as a prophylactic treatment for earlobe keloids in identified keloid formers. It involves the use of pressure earrings, which exert pressure between 15-40 mmHg on the earlobe after an excision of keloids on the earlobe (Gauglitz *et al.*, 2011). This therapeutic

approach yields the best result if the rings are worn all day; however, optimal results are less achieved because patients rarely adhere to the routine because of discomfort from wearing the ear rings(Slemp & Kirschner, 2006). Although the exact mechanism of action is not clear, it is hypothesized that the applied pressure decreases the blood supply to the tissues, which consequently causes the death of the tissues due to hypoxia(Mrowietz & Seifert, 2009). It has been demonstrated to produce between 70-90% improvements, although it has never resulted in complete resolution(Butler *et al.*, 2008). Compression therapy can be used in other forms of keloids where a special garment is made to allow for continuous application of pressure to the target site(Bae-Harboe, Harboe-Schmidt, Graber, & Gilchrest, 2014).

Intralesional Steroid Injection: Intralesional steroid injection has been demonstrated to produce relatively high effectiveness when used as a first-line therapy in keloid treatment(Butler *et al.*, 2008). Topical preparations of steroids have been used with few successes reported(Murray, 1993). Steroids affect their therapeutic function by inhibiting the synthesis of Nitric oxide synthase (NOS), which consequently inhibits the synthesis of collagen, glycosaminoglycan, and fibroblast degeneration(Gauglitz *et al.*, 2011). Triamcinolone acetonide is the most widely used intralesional steroid preparation; however, other available preparations include hydrocortisone acetate, methylprednisolone, and dexamethasone(Mrowietz & Seifert, 2009). Recurrence rates when lesions are treated with corticosteroids range anywhere from less than 10% to upwards of 30%(Andrews *et al.*, 2016). Reported side effects of corticosteroid treatments include atrophy of normal local tissue, local hypopigmentation/hyperpigmentation, and telangiectasia(Mari *et al.*, 2015).

Cryotherapy/Cryosurgery: This involves the use of liquid nitrogen to freeze the keloid lesion(Trace *et al.*, 2016). The freezing of the lesion induces cellular damage by anoxia, vascular damage, and the blocking of capillary perfusion in the lesion. (Gauglitz *et al.*, 2011). Cryotherapy has been used as a monotherapy; however, it has been demonstrated to have a better therapeutic index when used in conjunction with another therapeutic option(Mari *et al.*, 2015). Cryotherapy followed by steroid injection has

produced the best results. Reports have indicated that cryotherapy produces the best results when used for small lesions and facial keloids(Alster & Tanzi, 2003). Side effects associated with cryotherapy include permanent hypo and hyperpigmentation, moderate skin atrophy, blistering, and postoperative pain, among others(Mrowietz & Seifert, 2009). This treatment method is mostly practiced by unlicensed, unorthodox practitioners in Nigeria.

Surgical excision: Complete excision of keloid lesions without any adjunct therapy has resulted in higher reoccurrence rates (40%-100%) owing to it stimulating collagen synthesis, thus resulting in rapid regrowth of the lesion and often precipitating a larger regrowth(Davidson *et al.*, 2009). Core extirpation, which is a modified surgical approach, was reported to result in as much 63% improvement when used to treat keloid lesions (Rathee, Kundu, & Tamrakar, 2014). Core extirpation involves the removal of the fibrous core of the lesion, leaving the surrounding skin tissue(Alster & Tanzi, 2003). The combination of surgical excision of keloid with adjunct therapies significantly increases the outcome of treatment(Butler *et al.*, 2008).

Radiotherapy: This treatment is best used as an adjunct to surgical excision, with the best results recorded when done within the first two weeks of surgery(Kelly, 2009). Different dosages of radiotherapy have been employed by different groups, with success achieved. Abdus-Salam *et al.* (2016) recorded 85.5% success rate by administering two doses of 6Gy over a period of a week post-surgery, while Ogawa (2019) reported success by administering 5Gy daily doses between two and four days as a monotherapy. Radiation exerts its therapeutic activity by inducing apoptosis of keloid tissue and hence restoring the balance of the wound healing system and also by exerting a strong anti-inflammatory effect(Wolfram *et al.*, 2009; Ogawa, 2017). The most commonly used modality is external beam radiotherapy, specifically electron beam radiotherapy (Tziotzios, Profyris, & Sterling, 2012). The major drawbacks to radiotherapy include hyperpigmentation, pruritus, erythema, and risk of radiation-induced malignancy(Stahl *et al.*, 2010)

Boa Constrictor fat and Shea Butter: Topical therapeutic preparations sourced from animal and

plant products are an integral part of traditional African therapy. Shea butter, locally called Ori amo have been used in many preparations solely or in addition to other products(Ozioma & Ozioma, 2019). Pharmacological studies have established the therapeutic efficacy of shea butter in many conditions, especially dermatological conditions (Dennie, 2012). Boa constrictor fat, rich in essential fatty acids and shea butter have been used independently and jointly in the local treatment of keloids (Datubo-Brown and Blight, 1990). Anecdotal reports have shown some therapeutic efficacy of this material against keloid growth, especially with smaller keloids. Olaitan et al. (2011) reported some degree of efficacy of these preparations against keloids, although fish oil produced a more significant outcome. These oils are hypothesized to achieve their therapeutic function owing to their high content of Omega-3 fatty acids, especially Eicosapentaenoic acid (EPA).

QUALITY OF LIFE OF KELOID FORMERS

Skin lesions have long been established to have a negative impact on the psychosocial well-being of patients. Keloids, however, have been reported to exert a more debilitating effect on the quality of life of patients, especially among Caucasians (Lemonas *et al.*, 2015). Cosmetic unsightliness, especially among women, unsatisfactory treatment outcomes, and physical restrictions associated with Keloids have been major sources of psychological trauma for formers(Bock, Schmid-Ott, Malewski, & Mrowietz, 2006). Keloids are debilitating, especially to women, due to the shift in the acceptable societal standard of appearance in recent times. The majority of formers sought therapy for their Keloids owing to the fact that they have lost opportunities such as marriage proposals, jobs, restriction in choice of clothing, and the attitude of pity or worse, irritation that non-formers display towards keloid formers (Unpublished interview).

KNOWLEDGE, ATTITUDE AND PERCEPTION ABOUT KELOIDS AMONG NIGERIANS.

A pilot survey within Ibadan metropolis, a city in south-west Nigeria, revealed a minimum of eight alternative/unorthodox keloid removal centers in the city. Two centers that kept their clientele list showed that there is an average of 42 patients using the centers

per month. The majority (65%) of the keloid formers that sought therapy in these centers were female, with keloids located on the head and neck region accounting for most of the cases seen, followed by parts not usually covered by clothing. Anecdotal evidence revealed an average of four new cases of keloids seen on every clinic day at the University College Hospital, Ibadan. An informal survey to sample the opinion of the populace revealed that about 60% of respondents know at least one person who has Keloids. These are suggestive that the current available estimates do not accurately represent the burden of the condition, as the majority of keloid patients either seek traditional/unorthodox therapy or no therapy at all.

The survey, which also assessed the knowledge, attitude, and perception about keloids, revealed 80% of respondents know what keloids are, but just 37% of these know what could cause the disease. None (0%) of the 43 respondents were keloid formers, and Non-formers believed that knows what could cause Keloids know that skin color pigment (melanin) is associated with Keloid development. This is indicative of the lack of knowledge about Keloids in our population. The majority of the formers (56%) felt stigmatized and attributed the stigmatization to having lesions in conspicuous parts of their body. This is similar to the report of Olaitan (2009), who reported (48.9%) complained of stigmatization owing to their keloid lesion(s). The survey and unpublished interviews showed that women constitute the bulk of patients seeking therapy for Keloids and the majority of keloid therapies were sought by formers whose lesions are on the head and neck region, followed by parts of the body usually not covered by clothing.

About 16% of non-formers in the survey said they cannot share utilities with keloid formers. Above 36% and 11% of survey participants will not be romantically involved with formers or allow their children to fraternize with formers, owing to their disgust for keloid formers. About 33% of employers that took part in the survey would prefer to employ non-formers, while 14% would rather not employ formers at all. These statistics agree with the report of Olaitan (2009), who reported that about 35.8% of keloid formers complained that keloids limit their

social interaction, 32% of formers said their spouses are unhappy about them having keloids.

These findings and more establish the need for a policy that aims to address stigmatization against keloid formers and prohibit discrimination by employers against recruiting qualified individuals because of their keloid lesions.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Keloid pathogenesis and treatment remain an enigma for biomedical scientists and clinicians alike. The unavailability of a suitable model organism and consequentially dearth of keloid pathological studies has reduced the pace of development of possible and more efficient therapeutic interventions against keloid. This further necessitates the need to definitively understand the pathogenesis and the genetics of Keloids in a bid to develop better treatment/management protocols.

There is currently no prevalence figure for Keloids in Nigeria as there is no standing policy in the country for tracking the incidence of Keloids, sensitization to Keloids, and prohibition of stigmatization against formers. Keloids continue to be a source of trauma to formers due to stigmatization and marginalization. Unfortunately, the plight of victims goes largely unnoticed because there are more questions than answers about the condition. The lack of a health policy framework, permanent treatment option, high cost of hospital treatment options, among others, have encouraged the proliferation of uncontrolled keloid therapy practice in the country.

Risk factors for Keloids are largely uncontrollable, thus making the chance of limiting the exposure of genetically predisposed individuals to the risk factors slim. There is a need for a scan of the genome of the Native African population for genetic signatures associated with the condition. This will help in the development of genetic screening protocols in order to identify individuals at risk of developing Keloids.

The awareness of Keloids is currently poor or virtually non-existence thus the prevailing negative beliefs and attitudes of the general populace towards the condition and the formers. There is an urgent need for an intervention aimed at sensitizing the general populace about the disease condition to avert a possible surge in

the incidence of Keloids due to increased demand in elective surgical procedures and the greater acceptability of cosmetic modifications such as tattooing and body piercings in the Nigerian population.

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